

MARKETING TACTICS IN TIMES OF COVID-19**A. Kumar¹, A. Gawande² and V. Brar³**¹Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra, India²Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, Maharashtra, India³S.N.G. Institute of Management & Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India**ABSTRACT**

The Covid-19 coronavirus outbreak is a human tragedy affecting billions of people in this world. The outbreak also imposed negative impacts on the global economy, industries corporations, and small and medium enterprises (SMEs). As the effects of Covid-19 have been profound and pervasive, this review was structured around the pandemic and how it has altered the core marketing concepts, the context of marketing tactics, and marketing strategies. Covid-19 has changed everything radically for people as they work and shop from home. So to stay relevant and competitive the companies have had to depend upon online marketing tactics, artificial intelligence, and machine learning techniques to identify and promote their services and products through emails and advertisements to their target audience. Corporate social responsibility and consumer ethics have also been used to endorse products as a new marketing strategy. Interviews with ten entrepreneurs showed that tactical marketing had a significant role to play.

Keywords: Marketing Tactics, Strategies, Covid-19, Pandemic.

Introduction

The Covid-19 coronavirus outbreak is a human tragedy affecting billions of people in this world. The outbreak also imposed negative impacts on the global economy, industries corporations, and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) (Omar et al., 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic, as an uncommon situational and relevant factor, has critical ramifications for the comprehension of purchaser moral dynamic during the pandemic just as conceivably post-pandemic over the long haul. During the pandemic, various customers were grounded to their homes with restricted outside access aside from the web, because of lockdown and other social separating measures. Customer dynamic can be silly during emergencies like the current pandemic, as confirmed by accumulating of food, meds, cleanliness and sterilization items, and even tissues everywhere in the world. A few might contend that alarm purchasing (incl. amassing) is the level-headed buyer conduct during emergencies like this with an essentially undeniable degree of vulnerability. So how does one go about solving this issue at the level of the customer?? (He and Harris, 2020). Hence, He and Harris (2020) have projected a solution for organizations to move towards more certified and legitimate corporate social responsibility and different marketing tactics in terms of advertisements and promotions to

address dire worldwide social and ecological difficulties.

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Literature Review

He and Harris (2020) have elaborated on corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a marketing tactic to boost their sales in the future. For example in the UK, THE CMA (Competition and Marketing Authorities) have exhorted the companies to follow an ethical line of conduct during the pandemic and use their CSR to benefit people and not exploit them in these difficult times by exercising refrain from giving people overstated claims of their products at higher prices (Butler, 2020). Other examples from the UK regarding CSR that are worth consideration for instance are: UK manufacturing organizations changed their plants to deliver ventilators, individual defensive gear, hand sanitizer, etc., with some of them giving, rather than selling, these items. Media communications goliath Vodafone presented free admittance to limitless versatile information for a large number of its compensation month to month clients, what's more, redesigned its weak compensation month to month clients to limitless information offer free of charge (BBC, 2020).

Grocery stores in the UK have dispensed opening times explicitly for the older and NHS staff and gave Easter eggs and general food to food banks and beneficent associations (Fairshare.org.uk, 2020; Lindsay, 2020).

The UK tea brand PG tips joined forces with Re-draw in (a beneficent association expecting to tackle the issues of social confinement and dejection for more established individuals) to train volunteers to call the most established in the UK during the lockdown (He and Harris, 2020). Organizations gave their unique business crusade broadcast appointment to advance great motivations.

Banks deferred revenue on overdrafts over a timeframe. What's more, the rundown goes on. An association's real CSR will fabricate more grounded compatibility among its clients and the overall population, as they have developed solid assumptions from driving brands, especially their ideal brands, during the current emergency as to their endeavours in fighting the infection (He and Harris, 2020).

Endorsing customer ethics as a marketing strategy during the pandemic has given freedom and time to the purchasers to consider the essential importance of utilization and the effect of their utilization on themselves as well as on others and the overall society and the climate (He and Harris, 2020).

Before the pandemic, purchasers in the created world have underestimated how their fundamental requirements, for example, food and asylum, can be handily met through the wide accessibility of different items and administrations that can help address those issues. Customers were "spoilt" with "decision over-burden". Besides, utilization is additionally determined by buyers' quest for products and enterprises that can help meet they're higher social (e.g., social having a place and confidence) what's more, self-realization needs (Maslow, 1943).

The pandemic stunned buyers with the thought and even a profoundly likely reality that their fundamental requirements probably won't be met as in food and necessities probably won't be accessible to them. While in the created world, fundamental buyer needs are still liable to be met, there will be a few moves in terms of how shoppers appreciate and esteem those requirements being met. At a similar time, it

changes buyers' point of view on the most proficient method to seek after higher social and self-completion needs. There is probably going to be a critical move towards dependable and prosocial utilization in the sense that shoppers deliberately think about how to devour and make item/brand decisions to be more mindful of themselves, others, the society, and the climate (He and Harris, 2020).

The pandemic has shown purchasers a thing or two that we are interconnected as far as the effect of our item/image decisions; consequently, we ought to be aware of those decisions. Customers will be more liable to pass judgment on themselves or others to frame a crucial assessment of ones' self-ideas (purchaser character) in light of one mindful utilization and prosocial item/brand decisions (He, Li, and Harris, 2012).

In all, shoppers' more significant level of social and self-realization needs will be bound to be met by their mindful and prosocial practices as buyers. Albeit dependable and prosocial buyers will turn into a bigger customer portion, the pandemic will develop an alternate buyer section that centers on intuition epicurean satisfaction (He, Li, and Harris, 2012).

The whirlwind pace of the spread of Covid-19 expected associations to grow such innovative deftness as to comprise adaptability to the point of hypermobility! While creative observers commended the requirement for key deftness to make new business sectors that reach new shoppers and clients pandemic constrained organizations required chiefs and supervisors to create frameworks, activities, and strategies that arrived at the client's doorstep! During the covid-19 pandemic, the governmental and private organizations quickly adapted market motivating tactics to educate and manage indispensable services, supply and demand, and behaviour of the people in general. A key aspect of this is the exponentially augmented move to online communications and alteration that has been a very rapidly growing medium at least temporarily during lockdown situations all industries and divisions found the change prompt and insightful. Whether this alteration merely enhanced an on-going development or is rescindable is arguable (Butler, 2020).

A qualitative study done in Malaysia revealed the impact of lockdown and restrictions

imposed by the government on the SME (Small and Medium Enterprises) led to supply chain disruptions, cash disparity, stimulus packages were disrupted and there was a huge rise in bankruptcy (Omar et al, 2020). The people re-adapted to new marketing strategies like online marketing and the government-assisted those in need with an economic business stimulus package called PRIHATIN (Omar et al., 2020). According to Rautela and Agrawal, (2020), the rise of technology (AI), and digital marketing via social media, telecom, online retail platforms, has changed the elements of the business world. Simulated intelligence holds the gigantic potential for limitlessly adjusting how marketing and advertising are done. New marketing instruments like biometrics, voice, and conversational UIs offer numerous approaches to add an incentive for brands and customers the same. These developments all convey comparable attributes of hyper-personalization, proficient spending, adaptable encounters, and profound bits of knowledge. The innovation helps the entirety of the advertisers to act in a superior way, to comprehend the requirements, needs, and requests of their clients, and empower them to focus in a superior manner during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Digital marketing has been a huge success during the pandemic. Modern showcasing is utilized in the advanced stage it is more adaptable. It can be gotten to on any gadget which implies that the organization has higher odds of coming to the worldwide crowd. It can likewise effectively adjust to the changes and have no issue in keeping up the most recent promoting patterns. All of these things help up to construct client steadfastness, trust just as overall brand acknowledgment (Rautela and Agrawal, 2020).

Interviews with ten entrepreneurs

The Global Gap Report 2020, highlights the areas with highest gender gaps, emerging jobs for future economies being one of the main concerns. These emerging jobs profiles comprise of Product Development, Data and AI, Engineering and Cloud Computing. The participation of women in most of these job roles is less than 30% in most of the economies in which Engineering and Cloud Computing

record the lowest representation of women that is 12 -15%. The figure below is representative of the Indian scenario where one can observe a similar trend vis-à-vis the global trend.

Women have focused mainly on the baseline skills over time but AI and cloud computing are the skills that should be targeted for greater participation in the emerging jobs roles. Thus, up-skilling and specific trainings seem to be the probable solution to the problem of representation of women in an arena where presence of women is at a nascent stage.

Interviews with ten entrepreneurs

Collective consideration of the ten respondents showed the following tactics used:

1. Support Your Customers About How Your Company is Responding to the Pandemic
2. Transfer Your Brand Online to Stay Connected to Your Customers
3. Revive Customer Experience Strategies to Relook at End-to-End Deals Processes
4. Zero in on Strengthening Your Relationship With Your Customers
5. Mix Empathy in Your Marketing Communications
6. Actualize an Agile Strategic Pricing Model to Improve Margins
7. Think about Your Company Values During this Lockdown and Refocus your Commitment Strategies
8. Stay away from the Hard Sell and Reaffirm your Commitment to the long run
9. Use Marketing Technology to Stay Connected to Customers When Working Remotely
10. Help Your Customers Navigate the Situation and Pivot as Necessary

Conclusion

Covid-19 has changed everything radically for people as they work and shop from home. So to stay relevant and competitive the companies have had to depend upon online marketing tactics, artificial intelligence, and machine learning techniques to identify and promote their services and products through emails and advertisements to their target audience. Corporate social responsibility and consumer ethics have also been used to endorse products as a new marketing strategy.

References

1. BBC (2020). 'Coronavirus: Vodafone offers 30 days free mobile data', The BBC. Accessed at <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/technology-52066048>.
2. Butler, C. (2020). How to survive the pandemic, Chatman House: The World Today, <https://www.chathamhouse.org/publication/s/twt/how-survivepandemic>.
3. Butler, S. (2020), New UK taskforce to crack down on coronavirus profiteers. The Guardian, <https://www.theguardian.com/business/2020/mar/20/new-UK-taskforce-to-crack-down-on-coronavirus-profiteers>.
4. Fairshare.org.uk (2020), Co-op to donate food worth £1.5 million to FareShare to feed those at risk of hunger during Coronavirus crisis, accessible at: <https://fareshare.org.uk/news-media/press-releases/co-op-to-donate-food-worth-1-5-million-to-fareshare-to-feed-those-at-risk-of-hunger-during-coronavirus-crisis>.
5. He, H., and Harris, L. (2020). The impact of Covid-19 pandemic on corporate social responsibility and marketing philosophy. *Journal of Business Research*, 116, 176-182.
6. He, H., Li, Y., & Harris, L. (2012). Social identity perspective on brand loyalty. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(5), 648–657.
7. Lindsay, J. (2020), Aldi donates Easter eggs to food banks and local charities', Metro, accessible at: <https://metro.co.uk/2020/04/04/aldi-donates-easter-eggs-food-banks-local-charities-12507475>.
8. Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*. 50(4), 370–396.
9. Omar, A.R.C., Ishak, S., and Jusoh, M.A. (2020). The impact of Covid-19 Movement Control Order on SMEs' businesses and survival strategies. *Malaysian Journal of Society*, 16(2), 139-150.
10. Rautela, A., and Agrawal, P. (2020). A Review Of Modern Marketing Tools In The Era Of Covid-19. *Palarch's Journal Of Archaeology Of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(6), ISSN 1567-214x